

A Brief Study On Water Quality Liable for Contaminating the River Padma, Rajshahi

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Abstract

Rajshahi is the fourth largest city corporation in Bangladesh with a population of 8 lakhs. Everyday a large amount of waste water is produced throughout the city mainly consisting of domestic waste accompanied by a considerable amount of industrial waste. A lion share of this waste water is found to be discharged in an untreated manner directly in the river Padma. Ultimately river Padma is becoming contaminated day by day. As a result, the aquatic life in Padma and the overall fertility of agricultural land around the river are affected potentially. The aim of this study to assess the physiochemical characteristics of the waste water and to find out the major contaminating parameters. For this purpose, samples were collected from the ten suitable point around Rajshahi city. In the laboratory various water quality tests were performed and compared to the standards of WHO, FAO & BECR. Overall, the study has shown some findings regarding contaminants, which are beneficial for the PADMA river from being polluted.

Keywords: River Pollution, Physiochemical Analysis, Domestic Sewage, Contaminating Parameters.

1 Introduction

Water is one of the vital elements of the environment as well as a most important natural resource. Civilization is next to impossible excluding water. But the rapid growth of civilization and urbanization at an accelerated rate is mostly accountable for the pollution of this resource. Nowadays pollution of water and deterioration of water quality is a burning issue all over the world, Bangladesh is also not an exception. In Bangladesh surface water sources are getting contaminated mostly. House hold waste, municipal sewage even Industrial wastes also being discharged untreated in the adjacent rivers. Textile industries annually discharge 56 million tons of waste, 0.5 million tons of sludge in most contaminated river, the Buriganga and sewage of almost whole city is discharged into it as well (River water quality report 2014). According to the report of Ministry of Environment and Forest, the quality water of almost all major rivers are getting deteriorated in a comparison of the period 1975-1977 & 2010-2014. Padma in also not out of this trend. According to the statistics, by the early 20th century, the complete natural river in the world tends to zero, which is very alarming and shocking news for the environment and the ecosystem (Perrow and Davy, 2002). The problems of urban river pollution and ecological damage are becoming more and more crucial for the environment (Wang et al., 2012). So it's high time to take steps to save our natural valuable resources and also for our sound survival.

The Padma is one of the major rivers in Bangladesh. It is the main tributary of the Ganges which is flowing through Rajshahi city and which is a city of around 8 lakhs of population. In this city every day a huge amount of waste water is produced form house hold, market, commercial area, hospital, educational institution as well as industries and a significant share of this waste water is being discharged into the river Padma untreated. This untreated mixed sewage may potentially contaminate the water of the river which will be dangerous for the aquatics in the river and subsequently an imbalance in the ecosystem may get developed. Also the cultivable land along the side of Padma may turns into barren one. Considering this circumstances this study aimed at the investigation of the physiochemical characteristics of the water that is directly being discharged into river Padma through the sewage line and compare the result to the guideline for Environment Quality Standard (EQS) provided by environment conservation rule (1997), FAO and WHO to show whether it's fit to discharge without treatment or not. And this study also discuss what steps to be taken before the discharge of this influents.

1.1 Study area

Rajshahi city lies between 24°21´ and 24°25´ North latitudes and between 88°32´ and 88°40´ East longitudes, with an area of about 96.68 sq. km with 30 wards. One side of the boundary of the Ward no. 4, 7, 9, 12, 22, 23, 24, 25, 28 and 29 is bank of Padma that's why the sewage of these wards is discharged into Padma. In this study ward no. 9, 12, 22, 23, 24 and 25 are taken into consideration.

Figure 1. Ward map of Rajshahi city corporation

2. Methodology

2.1 Sample collection

Samples were collected from the area mentioned above. The site of the sample collection is marked in Fig. 2 and the location of sample collection is presented in Table 1. Sample were collected from the mentioned location and required tests were worked out at the Public Health Laboratory of Rajshahi University of Engineering and Technology (RUET), Rajshahi.

Table 1. Location of sampling

Sl.	Site no.	Sample name	Ward no.	Site name
1	1	S1	9	Boro Kuthi Ghat
2	2	S2	9	Darga Para
3	3	S3	9	Behind Rajshahi college
4	4	S4	12	Behind Munnujan school
5	5	S5	22	Kumar para mondir
6	6	S6	22	Kolponar hall-i
7	7	S7	22	Kolponar hall-ii
8	8	S8	23	I badh
9	9	S9	24	Shaheed minar, Talaimari
10	10	S10	25	Boubazar, Talaimari

Figure 2. Location of sample collection.

2.2 Sampling technique

From the selected 10 stations waste water were collected in clean water bottle. The sampling was done 10 a.m. to 3 pm. Samples were collected nearly from the center of the discharge point, at approximately 25 % of the water

depth, where the turbulence was maximum and the possibility of solids settling was minimum. The sampling bottle were filled up to 75% of it's capacity. Skimming the water surface or dragging the channel bottom as well as aeration of the sample was avoided as far as possible. Collected samples were transported to the laboratory and put to test within 2 hours of collection.

2.3 Experiment method

For this study to determine the parameters, both of experimental methods and automatic devices are used. The physical tests are mostly worked out using the specific standard devices and the chemical tests are also performed according to the standard methods. The pH, DO and BOD were measured by a digital meter (DZB-718 Portable Multi-Parameter Water Analysis Meter). Turbidity was analyzed by Turbid meter TN-100, EUTECH instruments. EC was determined by Electric conductivity meter. Titrimetric method using standard 0.02 N NaOH and phenolphthalein as indicator was used to determine CO₂. Total alkalinity was determined by titration with a standard 0.02 N sulfuric acid solutions and methyl orange as indicator. COD was determined by conventional titrimetric method using standard ammonium oxalate[(NH₄)₂C₂O₄] and potassium permanganate[KMnO₄]. Chloride was determined using silver nitrate of 0.014 N with potassium chromate indicator by titration. Hardness was determined using HI-3812 hardness test kit. TDS and TSS are measured using conventional method of suction and drying.

3 Results and Discussion

All the parameters are determined by the standard method mentioned and they are compared to the standard for Bangladesh and international (FAO & WHO). Except some results most of the results are within the standard limit of Bangladesh, FAO as well as WHO but the values are a bit high. The results are represented in tabular form in the Table-2 and Table-3.

Sample No.	pH	EC (μ-moh/cm)	CO ₂ (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)	TS (mg/L)	TDS (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)	Hardness (mg/L)
S1	6.68	1600	1.3	12.78	850	400	450	150
S2	6.69	2100	1.76	19.88	820	490	330	180
S3	6.83	2000	1.76	16.66	470	370	100	120
S4	7.02	1400	2.2	34.1	770	430	340	240
S5	6.47	2000	4.4	12.12	560	390	170	210
S6	6.87	2100	2.64	59	910	550	360	150
S7	6.93	1900	1.76	44.54	620	420	200	90
S8	7.05	2100	3.52	13.38	480	340	140	210
S9	6.75	1600	2.2	12.24	700	450	250	120
S10	6.72	1800	2.64	12.61	630	480	150	240

Table 2. pH, EC, CO₂, turbidity, TS, TDS, TSS and Hardness of all sample

Table-3: Alkalinity, COD, BOD, DO, Total Acidity and Chloride content of all sample

Sample No.	Alkalinity (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	DO (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	Chloride (mg/L)	Temperature (°C)
S1	156	190	2.22	45	223.33	28
S2	370	420	1.66	82	297.78	27.35
S3	400	380	1.93	77	337.48	29
S4	150	350	1.84	79	258.08	28.2
S5	360	415	1.59	83	272.97	29.1
S6	350	300	1.84	68	312.67	26
S7	420	360	2.14	72	322.60	28.2
S8	380	256	2.28	70	287.85	29
S9	180	225	2.17	73	238.22	27.3
S10	200	260	2.32	65	258.08	27

Figure 3. Comparison of TDS & TSS

Figure 4. COD and BOD (mg/L) at different stations

Figure 5. Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L) at different stations

pH level varies from station to station. Highest value of pH found is 7.05 at Kolponar Hall and lowest one is 6.47 at Kumar para Mondir. All pH values are within limit according to Bangladeshi and FAO standard (6.0-8.5) but S5 is beyond limit according to WHO (6.5-8.5).

The Electric conductivity (EC) is the capacity of water to conduct current, which is caused by the presence of salts, acids and bases, called electrolytes, capable of producing cations and anions [4]. It's considered as a vital parameter for irrigation water as the increase in salinity hinders the growth of plants by lessening the water potential in the soil. In between 10 samples Electric Conductivity(EC) varies from 1600 to 2100 μ -moh/cm. Permissible limit for

Bangladesh, WHO and FAO for irrigation use is 2250, 1200 and 3000 μ -moh/cm respectively. All the sample satisfy the Bangladesh and FAO standard whereas none of them satisfy WHO standard.

Turbidity of water lowers the temperature of water body at the bottom and interferes with the passage of light. Low temperature is bad for aquatic life and lack of light is hazardous for aquatic plants. Various fine particle like food item, silt, pollen grain, dust etc. presents in the water make it turbid. As the samples are of municipal sewage, so it's natural to be turbid. Turbidity of different sample varies from 12.12 to 59 NTU whereas the Environment Quality Standard (EQS) for Bangladesh is 10 NTU. Most of the sample are within 20 NTU but the sample from Munnujan school and Kolponar Hll are extremely turbid.

Total dissolved solid (TDS) mostly consist of chemicals, soluble inorganic salt or organic matter. Sorensen et al., 1977 found lower productivity in algae at TDS concentrations greater than 1400 mg /L. Out of all samples lowest TDS found at I badh (S8) which is 340 mg/L and highest one is at Kolponar hall (S6) which is 550 mg/L. EQS for Bangladesh, WHO, FAO is 1000, 2100 and 2000 mg/L respectively. From the Figure. 3 it's evident that all of the samples are within the standard limit.

Lowest Total Suspended Solid (TSS) found at the point behind Rajshahi College (S3) which is 100 mg/L and highest is at Boro Kuthi Ghat which is 450 mg/L. EQS for Bangladesh is 100 mg/L. Here except S3 all sample exceeds the standard limit represented in Figure. 3.

Alkalinity is the capacity of the water to neutralize the acid compound and balancing the pH of water. Though it's beneficiary to the water system up to a permissible limit but the excessive amount of alkalinity may affect the aquatic environment and land in which it's used for irrigation. Usage of high alkaline water decreases the permeability of soil and causes water logging. The EQS for in Bangladesh is 150 mg/L for surface water. But the water discharging into Padma is with high alkalinity.

Environment Quality Standard (EQS) for Chemical oxygen demand (COD) in Bangladesh is 200mg/L. All of the sample exceed the limit of COD except the Boro Kuthi Ghat which is 190 mg/L.

Oxygen absorbed by the organisms present in the water is referred to as biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). The limit specified by Bangladesh standard is 40 mg/L. But here out of ten stations all exceeds the limit. The highest BOD found at Kumarpara Mondir which is 83 mg/L. Which will cause a high scarcity of oxygen available for aquatics.

Dissolved Oxygen limit for Bangladesh is more than 6 mg/L but here all the results are below the limit. And it's found at the Kumar para Mondir which is 1.59 mg/L. Which is very a little for the survival of aquatic lives.

Temperature of the discharge at all points were permissible according to standard it varied from 26-29.1 °C.

4 Conclusion

The wastewater, generated in the area of Rajshahi City Corporation considered, possesses a significant amount of contaminant. This domestic effluent dominated wastewater flow through the concrete drainage network and finally being disposed to the river Padma without any treatment continuously. Some of the parameters are not satisfactory to the standard limit, some are satisfactory but very close to the highest limit. So this untreated discharge may cause serious pollution potentially during dry season specially. Quality parameters at the station Kolponar Hall and Behind the Munnujan school mostly dissatisfactory to discharge into surface water body and use for irrigation moreover the discharge of this two points are higher than other stations. During dry season the water from Padma accompanied by this wastewater is used for irrigation, but the quality of this discharge is not fully satisfactory for irrigation which may affect the yield of crop and fertility of the land. Although the water body of Padma is not contaminated at high level but in long run it may be. So it's high time to take the proper steps.

5 Recommendations

To save the river Padma from the potential contamination risk some steps to be taken. All over the world, organizations and governmental institutions are concerned to save this resource form pollution and they are enforcing laws and taking preventive measures and techniques. The techniques that are being used globally some of them may be applied for Padma also, they are as follows,

- ❖ Proper treatment of the waste water before discharge into river.
- ❖ Establishment of water quality index (WQI) to assess the quality before dumping.

- ❖ Construction and continuous operation of Effluent treatment plant (ETP/CETP) to stop the dumping of untreated wastewater into Padma.
- ❖ Improvement of sanitation system.
- ❖ Increment of flow of river in dry season.
- ❖ Implementation of Integrated Watershed Management (IWM).
- ❖ Development of a system to observe the water quality periodically.

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